

Blockchain enhanced SECRET small cells for the 5G environment

Vipindev Adat, Ilias Politis, Christos Tselios, and Stavros Kotsopoulos

Wireless Communications Laboratory

University of Patras, Greece

{vipindev, ipolitis, tselios, kotsop}@ece.upatras.gr

Abstract—Network coding has emerged as a promising solution to the highly efficient and reliable network requirements for the next generation communication technology. Network coding enabled small cell environment can assure an efficient device to device communication with the high data rate. However, the security challenges inherent to network coding, like pollution attacks, drags a layer of concern over its implementation. Further, the re-encoding of packets at the intermediate nodes makes it difficult to secure network coding enabled communication using standard cryptographic techniques. Homomorphic message authentication codes and signatures are used to tackle this problem. We propose a network coding enabled small cell environment enhanced by blockchain to prevent pollution attacks. The architecture of this blockchain enhanced SECRET small cell along with an analysis of the communication overhead and latency issues are discussed in this paper.

I. INTRODUCTION

The fifth generation (5G) wireless networks are expected to unveil high data rate, low latency heterogeneous networks in the very near future. These networks are expected to serve applications using a massive number of ultra-reliable energy efficient devices. Along with the internet of things (IoT) paradigm and machine to machine communication, the 5G networks will be supported by new technologies like network virtualization and cloud RAN to achieve the stringent network requirements [1]–[3]. The initial studies are also pointing out to the diverse cell structure such as macro, pico and small cells that will form the future networks [4], [5]. These dense networks of devices, heterogeneous in network size, device capabilities, and radio access technologies, also demand a high quality of service with ultra-reliable, low latency and energy efficient applications. Network coding is again emerging as a key enabler to achieve these targets in the 5G world by ensuring resilient wireless networks to utilize the available resources to the maximum [6].

Network coding is a method of improving the network throughput by allowing intermediate nodes to code the packets instead of just forwarding them [7]. It can drastically enhance the performances of a peer to peer network. Random linear network coding (RLNC) can be considered as a more suitable approach for wireless networks [8], providing high resiliency against volatile network conditions. In a dense heterogeneous

small cell environment, RLNC can be used to ensure the quality of service as well as high throughput requirements. Network coding can facilitate efficient utilization of available bandwidth and energy efficient communication between the devices inside a small cell as well as devices in different small cells [9]. Authors in [6] discuss the feasibility and advantages of having a secure network coding enabled energy efficient (SECRET) small cell environment.

However, the 5G world also needs to tackle the security challenges arising with the internet of things and 5G [10]–[13]. Even though network coding helps to secure the traffic from eavesdropping and provide high resiliency towards packet dropping, it also comes with more challenging problems in security [14], [15]. Recoding of packets in the intermediate nodes being the fundamental idea of network coding, itself provides a vulnerability for malicious intruders to attack the network. A malicious node being part of a network coding enabled network, can pollute the packets in motion. Such attacks, called pollution attacks [16], can significantly deteriorate the performance of the network. The pollution attacks can spread over the network and have a catastrophic effect over the network throughput. Thus checking and preventing pollution attacks in the earliest stage is a major concern for network coding enabled environments. This paper discusses a blockchain enhanced approach for SECRET small cells secure against pollution attacks. This approach uses homomorphic message authentication codes to ensure the integrity of packets being transferred over the network and utilize a blockchain to enable the verification of tags across the network efficiently. The remaining sections of the papers as follows. Section II discuss the important literature regarding existing solutions against pollution attacks and SECRET small cells. Section III explains the architecture of the blockchain enhanced SECRET small cells followed by the analysis of the scheme in section IV. Section V explains the future works and concludes the paper.

II. BACKGROUND WORK

Security challenges of network coding schemes are first studied in [17]. The major security threats specific to network coding always aroused from the capacity of intermediate nodes to encode the packets. Once a malicious node is involved in the path of the packet between source to destination, it can easily inject pollution attacks by sending a malicious packet instead

of the genuine one. Since the original packets generated at the node will undergo different linear operations during the encoding, it is not possible to check the integrity of packets using the conventional security schemes. Moreover, An end to end encryption can help to detect the polluted packets only at the receiver end which substantially reduce the efficiency of the system. This leads to the study of pollution attacks and homomorphic cryptographic schemes to ensure security. Homomorphic signatures and message authentication codes enable the verification even after the original packets undergo linear computations. This feature helps to verify the integrity of RLNC packets during the transition.

Homomac [18] was the first proposal of homomorphic message authentication codes to ensure the integrity of network coded packets. A number of MACs (also called tags) were created at the source and attached to the packets to be transmitted. These tags can be verified at every node having the same secret key used to generate the tags. Along with a secure key generation system, Homomac paved the path for Homomorphic MAC-based integrity schemes for network coding. However, this scheme created another kind of attack called tag pollution attack where the malicious node modifies the tags attached to the packets instead of changing the packets. This would lead to dropping of genuine packets by a genuine node since it will not be able to verify the tags attached with the packets. This kind of tag pollution attacks reduces the throughput of the network and considerably reduces the efficiency of communication since genuine packets will be dropped during the tag verification process. Homomorphic signatures [19] were another solution to the problem. In homomorphic signatures, the sender signs the linear combination of packets using its private key and the receiving nodes can verify the signature for any linear combination of the original packets. However, this verification is computationally complex compared to the MAC schemes. MacSig [20] proposes a combination of homomorphic MAC and signature schemes to ensure the security of network coding. In MacSig, homomorphic tags are used to protect the data integrity and concept of padding for orthogonality is used to sign the tags and prevent tag pollution attacks. Along with a particular double random key distribution, MacSig ensures protection against a possible combination of malicious users. However, the security of this scheme was also depending on the efficiency of key distribution scheme. Esfahani et al. proposed a dual MAC-based integrity scheme [21] and incorporated the concept of MacSig with a better c-cover tree based key distribution scheme in [22]. They have been able to improve the efficiency of the schemes compared with MacSig. However, the security against a combination of malicious users still depended on the key distribution scheme. Also, the complexity of initial key distribution and the verification of signatures at intermediate nodes needs to be improved. Further, these schemes were not able to achieve the maximum security with respect to the attached tags because the intermediate nodes will be having only a set of keys, not all of them, due to the key distribution schemes. As a result of this, even though

Fig. 1: SECRET small cells scenario

the original packets may be attached with a larger number of tags, but the possibility of detecting malicious packets at a particular node is limited to the number of tags it can verify.

Adapting network coding to the small cell environment, it also needs to improve the existing security schemes accordingly. A dense heterogeneous small cell environment has a variety of devices with different computational and storage capabilities and different trust levels. Also, as per the 5G paradigm, the small cell environment is very likely to be supported by an SDN network at the cloud and computationally capable edge nodes. Based on these assumptions, we are studying the SEcure network Coding enabled Reduced Energy next generation (SECRET) mobile small cells for the 5G and beyond wireless technologies as shown in fig. 1. To ensure the security against pollution attacks in the SECRET small cells, a blockchain enhanced homomorphic MAC-based integrity scheme is proposed [23]. A blockchain [24] could act as a secure distributed ledger for sharing the tags between different users in the network. The architecture of the blockchain enhanced SECRET small cells and initial analysis of the proposed system is explained in the following sections.

III. BLOCKCHAIN OF SMALL CELLS: ARCHITECTURE

As explained in [23], the security scheme requires a blockchain to securely communicate the tags to different nodes in the network. However, we realize that the current proposal may not be efficient to be used in a real environment. As we move on to the next generation small cells, we expect to have a very high number of devices with a wide variety of attributes, including trustworthiness, computational capability, and storage capacity. If we create the blockchain considering the network of every user equipment, it is very likely that most of them may not have enough resources to process and maintain the blockchain on their own. This paper improves the previous work to adapt to the real-world scenario where we expect resource-constrained nodes in the network by pushing the blockchain to the edge. In the proposed architecture, we assume all end nodes in the network to be lightweight nodes

with restricted resources. The small cell heads (hotspots) are considered to be stronger nodes in terms of storage and processing capabilities. Further, these nodes are considered to be trustworthy as they are directly connected and verified to the central network. The blockchain is formed over the network of such small cell heads only instead of considering the complete user device environment. The mining process happens only at these edge nodes and also the blockchain is maintained by them. The end nodes are fed by these edge nodes with only the basic information to access the blockchain instead of storing the whole blockchain there. The proposed blockchain architecture is shown in fig 2. Now let us analyze how the system works. The whole security system is explained in two different workflows. The first one concentrates on how the blockchain is created and maintained while the second one explains the tag creation and sharing to ensure the integrity of packets.

A. Blockchain creation and maintenance

We consider a permissioned blockchain system in the model of Ethereum [25] which uses an energy efficient Proof of Stake (PoS) algorithm for block verification. In proof of stake algorithms, the verification of blocks is done by the participating nodes having the highest amount of stake instead of all nodes competing to verify the block. This considerably reduces energy usage and also reduce the requirement of a hard computational problem to verify the blocks. The blockchain deployment starts with the installation of a blockchain client at the edge nodes. Ethereum platform also supports the syncing of live nodes by default. However, each node has to be provided with the same genesis block to be able to sync with each other. The genesis block will contain the hash value of the blockhead along with the timestamp and difficulty level of the mining process. The initialization process ensures that every participating node is initialized with the same genesis block. The blockchain network is active as soon as the nodes set up their primary accounts and get synced. Each participating node will have its own public key for unique identification while verifying and signing the block. Now, the mining process and adding of a new block to the chain happens when any edge node receives some tags to be added to the blockchain. The nodes will wait for a collection period to see how many nodes initiates communication during that time. As soon as the collection period ends, the block verification process will start. In the PoS based verification process, the blocks are verified by a particular node with respect to some specific rules, according to the stake each node holds. In our proposal, the verification process is done by the node which has the highest number of packets to be received during the transmissions initiated at the particular collection period. It ensures that, if the verifier acts maliciously, then the largest loss of packets happens to that particular node itself. Further, the other participating nodes are capable of blacklisting the node, if the verification process is done maliciously. This ensures a trustless, still secure blockchain environment for tag sharing. The whole process is shown as a flow chart in fig. 3.

B. Tag creation at source and verification using the blockchain

The integrity of the network coded packets is still ensured solely by the homomorphic tags in our proposal. However, with the blockchain network ensuring a secure tag sharing between the nodes, this scheme requires a very simple key distribution and ensures the maximum security possible with the additional tags attached to the packets. Whenever a node initiates a communication, the tags are created by the source over the native packets that need to be passed. The tags are created using the pre-distributed secret keys as per the equation

$$Tag_l = \frac{\left(\sum_{j=1}^n P_{i,j} \times K_{l,j} \right)}{K_{l,j+1}}, \quad l \in (1, L) \quad (1)$$

where each packet $P_i = P_{i,j}$, $j \in [1, n]$ and the key set K_s to create tag Tag_l as explained in [23]. These tags are attached to the packets before encoding the generation of packets. Further, these tags need to be updated in the blockchain via the edge node. Thus the tags are sent separately to the edge node via the control channel as shown in fig. 2. The edge node creates the block transaction consisting of the relevant information including the destination address and generation number along with the source address. Any intermediate node receiving encoded packets along with the tags will look for the corresponding entry of tags in the blockchain. This requires the end node to request the corresponding entry of blockchain from the edge node and then checks the integrity of received packets using the tags. Once the tags are successfully added to the blockchain as explained in the subsection III-A, the tags are permanently available to all small cells in the network and every node can access the tags. The tag verification takes place in two different steps, as shown in the fig. 4. In the first step, the receiving node checks for the tag pollution attack and in the second stage, it checks for the data pollution attack. This process is repeated at every receiving node.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SCHEME AND ANALYSIS

The proposed scheme is still under testing and we analyzed an initial simulation of the system in MATLAB and KODO [26]. KODO is an enhanced library of C++ for network coding techniques. The KODO library enables users to test their own algorithms as well as provide the high-level APIs for most common techniques and examples of network coding. It is also associated with fifi library for finite field operations. We tested our algorithms to verify the near real-time latency for a small cell environment. The computational complexity and communication overhead due to the additional tags were tested with MATLAB simulations in order to check the trade-off between security and number of tags. The computational complexity and bandwidth overhead increase proportionally with the number of tags. It is checked for the different number of tags against different packet size to find out that the computational overhead at each node corresponds to the multiplications required for the tag creation and it counts to be $L \times (n+1)$ multiplications, where L is the number of tags and n is the packet size. Similarly, a bandwidth overhead of L/n

Fig. 2: Blockchain architecture for SECRET small cells

Fig. 3: A work flow diagram for blockchain implementation

per packet. However, each tag attached to the packet limits the security threat to $1/q$ probability where q is the finite field size we are using for the computations. We are using four tags per packets for our simulations using KODO operated in $GF(2^8)$.

The simulations in C++ using KODO were done to check the delay of transmission with and without the security scheme and thus to check the additional delay due to the verification of tags. Since we are still setting up a proper blockchain server of GO Ethereum, for the current simulations, we did not count the time delay due to the mining process. Instead, we used a database system based on bigchainDB [27] to log the tags and retrieve them whenever required. BigchainDB is a distributed database that has similar characteristics to a blockchain with high throughput and sub-second latency. The end to end network included a minimum number of 4 internal nodes acting as intermediate nodes. The network coding simulations were run on an Ubuntu 16.04 system equipped with Intel Core i7-4770K and 8GB RAM operating at 3.4GHz. Initial tests were run with a simple RLNC network sending UDP packets over the network and end to end communication was achieved within a delay of maximum 10ms. Further, we repeated the test with the tag verification process in place and an additional delay of less than 1ms is recorded. A final test with an attacker node in the network is also done to verify that the attack is successfully detected at the first genuine node after the attacker node. These tests were repeated and the average overhead of time delay was less than 1 millisecond.

Fig. 4: Flowchart of tag verification

V. CONCLUSIONS

The fifth generation wireless technology needs to serve applications requiring high data rate and ultra low latency at low energy consumption. The network coding enabled mobile small cells can play a significant role in ensuring the maximum throughput over the network. Security of these SECRET small cells against pollution attacks is important to ensure that the best performance is achieved. In this paper, we proposed a blockchain enhanced SECRET small cells to provide highly secure energy efficient communication considering the diverse resource-constrained environment that the 5G and IoT world is build of. This approach takes into consideration the possible resource-constrained nature of end nodes and utilize the capa-

bilities of edge nodes to deliver better performance in terms of computations and storage capacities in order to ensure secure network coding along with proper resource utilization.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Tselios and G. Tsolis, "On QoE-awareness through virtualized probes in 5G networks," in *2016 IEEE 21st International Workshop on Computer Aided Modelling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD)*, Oct 2016, pp. 159–164.
- [2] L. Bolivar, C. Tselios, D. Mellado, and G. Tsolis, "On the deployment of an open-source, 5G-aware evaluation testbed," in *IEEE International Conference on Mobile Cloud Computing, Services and Engineering (Mobile Cloud)*, March 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [3] E. Markakis, G. Mastorakis, C. X. Mavromoustakis, and E. Pallis, *Cloud and Fog Computing in 5G Mobile Networks: Emerging Advances and Applications*. Institution of Engineering and Technology, 2017.
- [4] G. Bianchi, E. Biton, N. Blefari-Melazzi, I. Borges, L. Chiaraviglio, P. Cruz Ramos, P. Eardley, F. Fontes, M. J. McGrath, L. Natarianni *et al.*, "Superfluidity: a flexible functional architecture for 5G networks," *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. 27, no. 9, pp. 1178–1186, 2016.
- [5] S. Mumtaz, K. M. S. Huq, J. Rodriguez, S. Ghosh, E. E. Ugwuanyi, M. Iqbal, T. Dagiuklas, S. Stavrou, L. Kanaris, I. D. Politis, A. Lykourgiotis, T. Chrysikos, P. Nakou, and P. Georgakopoulos, "Self-organization towards reduced cost and energy per bit for future emerging radio technologies - sonnet," in *2017 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, Dec 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [6] J. Rodriguez, A. Radwan, C. Barbosa, F. H. Fitzek, R. A. Abd-Alhameed, J. Noras, S. M. Jones, I. Politis, P. Galiotos, G. Schulte *et al.*, "Secretsecure network coding for reduced energy next generation mobile small cells: A european training network in wireless communications and networking for 5g," in *2017 Internet Technologies and Applications (ITA)*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 329–333.
- [7] R. Ahlswede, N. Cai, S.-Y. Li, and R. W. Yeung, "Network information flow," *IEEE Transactions on information theory*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 1204–1216, 2000.
- [8] T. Ho, M. Médard, R. Koetter, D. R. Karger, M. Effros, J. Shi, and B. Leong, "A random linear network coding approach to multicast," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 52, no. 10, pp. 4413–4430, 2006.
- [9] P.-V. Mekikis, A. S. Lalos, A. Antonopoulos, L. Alonso, and C. Verikoukis, "Wireless energy harvesting in two-way network coded cooperative communications: A stochastic approach for large scale networks," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 1011–1014, 2014.
- [10] V. Adat and B. Gupta, "Security in Internet of Things: issues, challenges, taxonomy, and architecture," *Telecommunication Systems*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 423–441, 2018.
- [11] I. Ahmad, S. Shahabuddin, T. Kumar, J. Okwuibe, A. Gurtov, and M. Ylianttila, "Security for 5g and beyond," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 2019.
- [12] C. X. Mavromoustakis, G. Mastorakis, and J. M. Batalla, *Internet of Things (IoT) in 5G mobile technologies*. Springer, 2016, vol. 8.
- [13] S. Yang, D. Yin, X. Song, X. Dong, G. Manogaran, G. Mastorakis, C. X. Mavromoustakis, and J. M. Batalla, "Security situation assessment for massive mimo systems for 5g communications," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 98, pp. 25–34, 2019.
- [14] J. Dong, R. Curtmola, R. Sethi, and C. Nita-Rotaru, "Toward secure network coding in wireless networks: Threats and challenges," in *2008 4th workshop on secure network protocols*. IEEE, 2008, pp. 33–38.
- [15] A. Antonopoulos and C. Verikoukis, "Cops: Cooperative statistical misbehavior mitigation in network-coding-aided wireless networks," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 1436–1446, 2017.
- [16] J. Dong, R. Curtmola, and C. Nita-Rotaru, "Secure network coding for wireless mesh networks: Threats, challenges, and directions," *Computer Communications*, vol. 32, no. 17, pp. 1790–1801, 2009.
- [17] N. Cai and R. W. Yeung, "Secure network coding," in *Proceedings IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory*, 2002, pp. 323–.
- [18] S. Agrawal and D. Boneh, "Homomorphic macs: Mac-based integrity for network coding," in *International Conference on Applied Cryptography and Network Security*. Springer, 2009, pp. 292–305.

- [19] D. Charles, K. Jain, and K. Lauter, "Signatures for network coding," in *2006 40th Annual Conference on Information Sciences and Systems*. IEEE, 2006, pp. 857–863.
- [20] P. Zhang, Y. Jiang, C. Lin, H. Yao, A. Wasef, and X. Shen, "Padding for orthogonality: Efficient subspace authentication for network coding," in *2011 Proceedings IEEE INFOCOM*. IEEE, 2011, pp. 1026–1034.
- [21] A. Esfahani, D. Yang, G. Mantas, A. Nascimento, and J. Rodriguez, "Dual-homomorphic message authentication code scheme for network coding-enabled wireless sensor networks," *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, vol. 11, no. 7, p. 510251, 2015.
- [22] A. Esfahani, G. Mantas, J. Rodriguez, and J. C. Neves, "An efficient homomorphic mac-based scheme against data and tag pollution attacks in network coding-enabled wireless networks," *International Journal of Information Security*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 627–639, 2017.
- [23] V. Adat, I. Politis, C. Tselios, P. Galiotos, and S. Kotsopoulos, "On Blockchain Enhanced Secure Network Coding for 5G Deployments," in *2018 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–7.
- [24] C. Tselios, I. Politis, and S. Kotsopoulos, "Enhancing SDN security for IoT-related deployments through blockchain," in *2017 IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (NFV-SDN)*, Nov 2017, pp. 303–308.
- [25] G. Wood, "Ethereum: A secure decentralised generalised transaction ledger," *Ethereum project yellow paper*, vol. 151, pp. 1–32, 2014.
- [26] M. V. Pedersen, J. Heide, and F. H. Fitzek, "Kodo: An open and research oriented network coding library," in *International Conference on Research in Networking*. Springer, 2011, pp. 145–152.
- [27] T. McConaghy, R. Marques, A. Müller, D. De Jonghe, T. McConaghy, G. McMullen, R. Henderson, S. Bellemare, and A. Granzotto, "Bigchaindb: a scalable blockchain database," *white paper, BigChainDB*, 2016.